

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) i_MM, ii_MM, iii_MM

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: i_MM

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0004 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=9.6830 (1) b=7.9269 (1) c=11.1395 (1)
 alpha=90 beta=94.199 (1) gamma=90

Temperature: 110 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	852.730 (16)	852.730 (16)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C9 H9 N3 O	?
Sum formula	C9 H9 N3 O	C9 H9 N3 O
Mr	175.19	175.19
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.365	1.365
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.094	0.094
F000	368.0	368.0
F000'	368.14	
h, k, lmax	19, 15, 22	0, 0, 0
Nref	7212	7195
Tmin, Tmax	0.972, 0.985	0.972, 0.985
Tmin'	0.962	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.972 Tmax=0.985
AbsCorr = NONE

Data completeness= 0.998 Theta (max)= 45.461

R(reflections)= 0.0230 (6296) wR2(reflections)=
S = 1.049 Npar= 487 wR= 0.0220 (7191)

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H1	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H5	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H12	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H6A	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H6B	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H8	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H11	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H9	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i,j) Components(s) for H10	6 Check
PLAT992_ALERT_5_C	Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by	14 Check

● **Alert level G**

PLAT005_ALERT_5_G	No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF	Please Do !
PLAT066_ALERT_1_G	Predicted and Reported Tmin&Tmax Range Identical	? Check
PLAT143_ALERT_4_G	s.u. on c - Axis Small or Missing	0.00010 Ang.
PLAT808_ALERT_5_G	No Parseable SHELXL Style Weighting Scheme Found	Please Check
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G	Absent Datum for _atom_sites_solution_primary ..	Please Do !
PLAT911_ALERT_3_G	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	10 Report
	11 2 2, -4 6 3, 4 8 5, -10 2 6, -5 5 6, 3 7 7,	
	-9 1 9, -2 6 10, -1 1 10, 4 1 10,	
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	219 Note
PLAT929_ALERT_5_G	No Weight Pars,Obs and Calc R1,wR2,S not Checked	! Info
PLAT961_ALERT_5_G	Dataset Contains no Negative Intensities	Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	0.946 Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 4.25 or SHELX Weight 4.25	
PLAT980_ALERT_1_G	No Anomalous Scattering Factors Found in CIF ...	Please Check

- 0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
- 0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
- 10 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
- 11 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

- 3 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
 - 0 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
 - 10 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
 - 2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
 - 6 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
-

Datablock: ii_MM

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0003 A

Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=6.9504(1) b=7.1579(1) c=16.8961(1)
 alpha=90 beta=91.365(1) gamma=90
 Temperature: 110 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	840.347(18)	840.347(18)
Space group	P 21/n	P 21/n
Hall group	-P 2yn	-P 2yn
Moiety formula	C9 H7 N3 O2	?
Sum formula	C9 H7 N3 O2	C9 H7 N3 O2
Mr	189.18	189.18
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.495	1.495
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.110	0.110
F000	392.0	392.0
F000'	392.18	
h, k, lmax	13, 14, 33	0, 0, 0
Nref	7098	7081
Tmin, Tmax	0.956, 0.974	0.847, 1.000
Tmin'	0.953	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.847 Tmax=1.000
 AbsCorr = NONE

Data completeness= 0.998 Theta(max)= 45.464

R(reflections)= 0.0190(6420)

wR2(reflections)=
 wR= 0.0220(7103)

S = 1.254

Npar= 501

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H1	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H5	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H12	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H8	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H9	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H10	6	Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H11	6	Check
PLAT250_ALERT_2_C	Large U3/U1 Ratio for <U(i, j)> Tensor(Resd 1)	2.2	Note
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82, N0.98A) O1 - H1 .	1.02	Ang.
PLAT992_ALERT_5_C	Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by	49	Check

● Alert level G

PLAT005_ALERT_5_G	No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF	Please Do !
PLAT143_ALERT_4_G	s.u. on c - Axis Small or Missing	0.00010 Ang.
PLAT153_ALERT_1_G	The s.u.'s on the Cell Axes are Equal ..(Note)	0.0001 Ang.
PLAT808_ALERT_5_G	No Parseable SHELXL Style Weighting Scheme Found	Please Check
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G	Absent Datum for _atom_sites_solution_primary ..	Please Do !
PLAT911_ALERT_3_G	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	3 Report
	7 4 2, -1 0 11, 1 4 15,	
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	232 Note
PLAT929_ALERT_5_G	No Weight Pars,Obs and Calc R1,wR2,S not Checked	! Info
PLAT961_ALERT_5_G	Dataset Contains no Negative Intensities	Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	1.078 Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.52 or SHELX Weight	3.52
PLAT980_ALERT_1_G	No Anomalous Scattering Factors Found in CIF ...	Please Check

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3 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
1 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
9 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
6 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

Datablock: iii_MM

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0005 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=8.9369(1) b=7.1050(2) c=16.1335(1)
 alpha=90 beta=97.740(1) gamma=90

Temperature: 110 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1015.09(3)	1015.091(13)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4	?
Sum formula	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4
Mr	512.80	512.80
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.678	1.678
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	1.379	1.379
F000	518.0	518.0
F000'	519.40	
h, k, lmax	17, 14, 32	0, 0, 0
Nref	8579	8569
Tmin, Tmax	0.738, 0.813	0.972, 0.985
Tmin'	0.570	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.972 Tmax=0.985
AbsCorr = NONE

Data completeness= 0.999 Theta(max)= 45.463

R(reflections)= 0.0170(7768) wR2(reflections)=
S = 0.939 Npar= 573 wR= 0.0170(8631)

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.
Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● Alert level C

PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H1	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H5	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H8	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H12	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H11	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H9	6 Check
PLAT218_ALERT_3_C	Constrained U(i, j) Components(s) for H10	6 Check
PLAT355_ALERT_3_C	Long O-H (X0.82, N0.98A) O1 - H1 .	1.02 Ang.
PLAT992_ALERT_5_C	Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by	23 Check

● Alert level G

PLAT005_ALERT_5_G	No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF	Please Do !
PLAT143_ALERT_4_G	s.u. on c - Axis Small or Missing	0.00010 Ang.
PLAT152_ALERT_1_G	The Supplied and Calc. Volume s.u. Differ by ...	17 Units
PLAT164_ALERT_4_G	Nr. of Refined C-H H-Atoms in Heavy-Atom Struct.	6 Note
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Cu1 (II) .	2.13 Info

PLAT808_ALERT_5_G	No Parseable SHELXL Style Weighting Scheme Found	Please Check
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G	Absent Datum for _atom_sites_solution_primary ..	Please Do !
PLAT911_ALERT_3_G	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	5 Report
	-8 1 6, 1 5 10, 1 6 11, 3 5 12, 2 2 13,	
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	208 Note
PLAT929_ALERT_5_G	No Weight Pars,Obs and Calc R1,wR2,S not Checked	! Info
PLAT961_ALERT_5_G	Dataset Contains no Negative Intensities	Please Check
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G	The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value	0.869 Note
	Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.58 or SHELX Weight 3.58	
PLAT980_ALERT_1_G	No Anomalous Scattering Factors Found in CIF ...	Please Check

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It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 04/06/2025; check.def file version of 30/05/2025

Datablock i_MM - ellipsoid plot

